

A STUDY ON POST COVID-19 PANDEMIC POTENTIAL EMPLOYEE TURNOVER DUE TO WORK - LIFE BALANCE IN AMBARNATH CITY

Mr. Premkumar Sivan Nair

Asst. Professor,

HOD - Department of Accounting and Finance,

D.S.P.M.'s K. V. Pendharkar College (Autonomous), Dombivli (east)

Abstract:

Employee turnover is a very common term used in business organization. An organization with large employee turnover is harmful, and have a far reaching effect on organization's productivity, profitability and its efficiency. Over the year, through research, many reasons for employee turnover came in to light. One of it is work - life balance. Perceptions and understandings about work - life balance have changed, periodically. Passing through the COVID-19 pandemic & staying at home for comparatively large amount of time with family, is effecting the idea of work – life balance. Employees are now aware about the possibilities of working from home which will also connect them with their family. As per a Research by Microsoft 41% of world population is planning to quit their job this year due to several reasons including to avoid pressure and slavery. Attrition rate in tech sector in India is up 23%. The reasons are many which includes stress, unavailability of work from home flexibility, choice of free – lancing, start- ups and understanding of volatile or uncertain life. Irrespective of causes, organization may suffer due to this change termed as pandemic Epiphany by Dr. Anthony C. Klotz. This research will help the organization to know about the causes and the suitable actions to be planned and executed for the smooth functioning.

Keywords: *Employee Turnover, COVID-19 Pandemic, Work-Life Balance*

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1. Introduction

1.1 COVID – 19 pandemic

India, as one of most affected country in the world, have faced many deaths and cases during the 2020 and 2021. A total of 3,44,37,307 cases reported in India out of which 4,63,550 were declared deceased. Many precautionary, controlling and eradivative measures were taken to diminish the effect of the virus. One such precautionary measure was a complete lockdown of physical activities. All trading business organization except essentials were refrained to do physical business. Fortunately, technological assistance were available and that supported the business organization largely. It enhanced the facility of work from home even to people to whom it was not allowed earlier.

1.2 Work – Life Balance

Generally a middle class person have life expectancy of 60 to 70 years out of which 55 to 60 years they dedicate to work and enjoy their life post retirement. During their working period, people easily defer other aspects of life which includes self, family and society. Evidently many lose their personal life due to heavy working habits. On the counter part it is also seen that many people are not in a good health condition to enjoy their post retirement life also. Many research has been done and proved that finding a work life balance is very important. Due to COVID 19 pandemic, this conception of life after retirement got hit hard as life has become very volatile. COVID 19 pandemic also gave new methods and avenues of earning to which many have adapted. In relation to work, they now know about the flexibility of work from home, which also saves their travelling time.

Now the question arises what is this flexibility is taken back?

1.3 Employee Turnover

The image of the organization depends on various factors of which employee turnover is one of them. Employee turnover means number or percentage of employees that leave an organization during a given period of time. Irrespective of the reason, an organization with high employee turnover is not considered to be ideal work place and hence needs to be improved. It is also referred as attrition rate. Post COVID 19 pandemic the lack of flexibility in working environment may lead to unsatisfied employees which might lead to employee turnover.

1.4 Pandemic Epiphany

Dr. Anthony C. Klotz, has rightfully coined the term *Pandemic Epiphany* as this COVID

19 pandemic has took and gave many things. Humans have tendency to adapt to the new change and hence changed their outlook towards life and what to prioritize between work and life.

2. Statement of problem and Need for study

2.1 Statement of Problem:

Due to the effect of COVID 19 pandemic many people lose their life and many were at the verge of it. This reminded people that life can be very volatile and uncertain. Lockdown and restrictive transportation also made people comfortable with a different working environment i.e. Work from Home. This working environment made people to be more associated and in touch with their family. Hence learned a new form of balance between their work and life. Mentality of people has changed and it can result in to employee turnover if they feel discomfort in working environment.

2.2 Need for Study

Employee Satisfaction is a pivotal part for any organization. In due course if the ideology and priorities of them are changing then a prudent organization have to adapt to the current situation. Hence it is needed to understand whether the priorities of employees is changing in relation to work and life balance and if yes will that result in employee turnover.

2. Literature review

Christian Wiradendi Wolor, Ahmad Nurkhin and Yudin Citriadin (2021) the study enlightens whether work from home is good or bad for work life balance

Chowdhury Abdullah Al Mamun and Md. Nazmul Hasan (2017) the study is based on employee turnover and sound retention strategy

Amelia Cecilia S. Reyes, Carlota A. Aquino and David Cababaro Bueno (2019) the study spreads light on why employees leave and factors resulting in resignation.

Lisa Callagher and Peter Smith (2017) the study enlightens us with innovation awards to retain the employees

Christian Wiradendi Wolor, Solikhah Solikhah, Nadya Fadillah Fidhyallah and Deniar Puji Lestari (2020) the study is about the effectiveness of e-learning, e-leadership and work - life balance on employee performances during COVID – 19

3. Objectives of study

1. To study the effect of work life balance on employee turnover
2. To study the discomfort of employees in current situation

3. To study the effect of demographics on working environment and employee turnover

4. Hypothesis

H0 – There is no significant relation between demographics on working environment and employee turnover

H1 – There is significant relation between gender and comfortable working environment

H2 – There is significant relation between gender and desire to switch their job

H3 – There is significant relation between gender and comfortable working environment

H4 – There is significant relation between gender and desire to switch their job

5. Scope of the Study

The study is focused on effect of COVID 19 pandemic on work life balance of an employee that can lead to employee turnover. This research is useful for business organizations to make employees retain and reduce attrition rate.

6. Research methodology

For the purpose of the study, primary data collection method is used. All responses were collected through structured questionnaire method for working population within Ambarnath city.

7. Tools & Techniques

The statistical analysis carried out in the study is being done using Google sheets. The statistical techniques used are chi-square and simple percentage analysis. Analyzed and interpreted data have been presented in the form of tables and figures.

8. Limitations of study

1. Research is limited to Ambarnath city
2. All responses were at respondents' discretion

9. Research Analysis

Table no 1 Demographics of Respondents

Sr.No	Demographic profile of respondents	Attributes	Frequency	Percentage
1	Gender	Male	64	54.70
		Female	53	45.30
2	Age	18 – 21 years	2	1.71
		21 – 25 years	39	33.33
		25 – 30 years	52	44.44

		30 – 40 years	20	17.09
		40 – 50 years	4	3.42
3	Type of employment	Government	5	4.27
		Private	112	95.73
4	Type of remuneration	Contract	2	1.71
		Salary	114	97.44
		Wages	1	0.85
5	Frequency of remuneration	annual	4	3.42
		Monthly	113	96.58
6	Annual Income	1 – 3 lakhs	49	41.88
		3 – 5 Lakhs	41	35.04
		5 – 10 Lakhs	24	20.51
		10 Lakhs & Above	3	2.56
7	Working Hours	4 – 6 hours	2	1.71
		6 – 8 hours	24	20.51
		8 – 10 hours	78	66.67
		Depends on Work	13	11.11
8	Travelling time	0 – 30 mins	29	24.79
		30 – 60 mins	10	8.55
		1 – 1.30 hours	35	29.91
		1.30 – 2 hours	21	17.95
		2 – 3 hours	15	12.82
		More than 3 hours	7	5.98
		More than 3 hours	7	5.98

Source – Primary Data

Table no 1 exhibits 117 respondents including male and female 54.7% and 45.3% respectively. Responses also include different age structure as 1.71% of 18 to 21 years, 33.33% of 21 to 25 years, 44.44 % of 25 to 30 years, 17.09 % of 30 to 40 years and 3.42% of 40 to 50 years. Proportion of Government employees is less at 4.27% in comparison to Private of 95.73%. 97.44% are salary earning respondent, 1.71 % of contract earning and only 0.85 % of wage earnings. 96.58% of respondent receive monthly remuneration while 3.42 % on annual basis. Income structure are of 41.88% of 1 to 3 lakhs, 35.04% of 3 to 5 lakhs, 2051% of 5 to 10 lakhs and 2.56% of above 10 lakhs. Working hours are also diverse as 1.71% have 4 to 6 hours, 20.51 % have 6 to 8 hours, 66.6% have 8 to 10 hours and 11.11% depend on work. In case of

physical working, respondents travelling time i.e. to and fro, 24.79% take 0 to 30 minutes, 8.55 % take 30 to 60 minutes, 29.91% take 1 to 1.30 hours, 17.95% take 1.30 to 2 hours 12.82% take 2 to 3 hours and 5.98 % take more than 3 hours.

Table No 2 Preferred Working Environment

Sr. no	Place	Frequency	Percentage
1	Work from home	66	56.41
2	Work from office	51	43.59

Source: Primary Date

From table no 2 it becomes explicitly clear that 56.41% of respondent Prefer Work from home while 43.59% prefer to work from office.

Table No 3 relation with Current employer

Benefits	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
Timely Salary	5.98	1.71	19.66	19.66	52.99
Adequate Salary	5.13	9.40	43.59	23.08	18.80
Adequate medical benefits	5.98	11.11	37.61	29.06	16.24
Flexibility of work from home	17.95	5.98	24.79	25.64	25.64
Traveling benefits	12.82	17.09	29.06	23.93	17.09
Paid leave during emergencies	9.40	7.69	22.22	27.35	33.33
Timely increment in salary	11.11	17.95	33.33	20.51	17.09
Target Pressure	11.11	15.38	39.32	17.95	16.24

Source: Primary

Table no 3 exhibits that employees strongly disagree on variety of cases. Focusing on flexibility of Work from home 17.95% completely disagree of receiving the benefit from the employer, 5.98% Disagree 24.79% is neutral, 25.64% agree that they receive the benefit while 25.64% strongly on the benefit.

Table no 4 Change in Priorities post COVID-19 COVID 19 pandemic

Change in Priorities	Frequency	Percentage
Agree	80	68.38
Disagree	7	5.98
Partially Agree	30	25.64

Source: Primary

Table no 4 shows that 68.38% of respondents agree that their priorities have changed after the COVID-19 COVID 19 pandemic. 25.64% partially agree and 5.98% disagree of changing priorities.

Table No 5 Switching Job

Switching of job	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	41	35.04
No	33	28.21
May be	43	36.75

Source: Primary

From table no 5 it is clear that 35.04% is sure about switching their current jobs while 36.75% is doubtful. Only 28.21% is sure about not switching the job.

10. Testing of Hypothesis

Table no 6 Chi square results

Variables	Calculated Value	Tabular Value	Degree of freedom	Level of significance
Gender & comfortable work place	1.26	3.84	1	5%
Gender & Switching Job	2.54	5.99	2	5%
Age & comfortable work place	3.61	9.49	4	5%
Age & comfortable work place	11.73	15.51	8	5%

From Table no 6 exhibits that all calculated values are less than tabular values and hence null hypothesis is accepted as there is no significant relation between demographics of respondent on comfortable work place and employee turnover

11. Findings & Suggestions

11.1 Findings

From the research it is clear that respondents i.e. employees are more comfortable with working from home irrespective of their demographics.

If the flexibility of WFH is not given then it can lead to discomfort of employees as depicted in table no 3

It is also clear that the priorities of employees is also changed due to COVID-19 COVID

19 pandemic A mass resignation can be projected, if not treated wisely

11.2 Suggestions

Organizations may allow employees to work from home if physical presence is not needed.

There can be a blended approach and a flexible working environment.

If any employee is trying to switch the job a proper retention measure should be taken.

12. Conclusion

COVID-19 COVID 19 pandemic started with a heavy toll on human lives and wellbeing but it has also changed the ideology, philosophy of many people. The approach towards life and work has changed. The thought “Health is wealth” is understood well now; due to which restrictions on employee can lead to attrition and eventually leading to shut down. Hence organizations should change according to the current scenario and viability.

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